

INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT OF INDIA—PRESENT AND FUTURE*

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It is customary for the President of the Society to select for his annual address a topic in which he is a specialist. I would make a slight departure from the accepted practice and would like to talk on a subject which is uppermost in the minds of all chemists in this country, namely, "Industrial Development of India—present and future". This topic would be in harmony with the aims and objects of the Society, which are primarily to encourage and foster the spirit of enquiry and original research, to protect and develop scientific life in this country and to promote the growth of cultural fellowship among chemists in general.

Under the Government of India Act 1935, the development of industries was a Provincial subject, but it was open to the Central Government to declare by law that the development of certain industries under Central control was expedient in the public interest. On such a declaration being made, the development of such industries could become a Central subject. No such action was, however, taken with the result that at the outbreak of hostilities in 1939, the development of industries remained wholly a provincial subject. The war necessitated central control and direction over industries, as India was the supply base for the armies in the Middle East and the Far East. The Eastern Group Supply Council, which was formed as a result, placed on India all demands which could be met from India. The Central Government naturally took upon themselves the responsibility for the supply of entire requirements of the Indian army, both at home and abroad. To discharge this onerous responsibility, it was found necessary to create the Department of Supply which was responsible not only for all the procurement activities of the Government but also for developing new capacity. A large number of scientific men were thus mobilised for discharging these responsibilities. How well this duty was performed could be gauged from the fact that during the years 1942-1946, 106 crores of rupees worth of chemicals, paints, gases and petroleum products were procured. The purchases on account of leather and tanned materials amounted to 23 crores of rupees, that of rubber items to 10 crores, and so on.

With the cessation of hostilities, the Government of India felt that this development which had taken place during the war should be stabilised and put on a firm basis. It was recognised that India's industrial development would have to be the result of conscious and deliberate planning and should not be left to haphazard and unco-ordinated efforts of private industrialists. In 1945, the Government of India made an important statement of India's industrial policy. In this, it was recognised that positive steps to encourage and promote the rapid industrialisation of the country to the fullest possible extent were an inescapable responsibility of the Government. A number of

* Presidential address delivered at 26th Annual General Meeting of the Indian Chemical Society, held on January 3, 1950 at Poona.

Panels were set up to report on the existing position of various industries. The general directive to the Panels was on the following lines:—

- (i) The panels should report on the scope and extent of development including the types of products which should be taken up for development either by private enterprise or by the State ;
- (ii) The extent to which technical advice from abroad may be necessary ;
- (iii) The availability and future requirements of technical personnel ;
- (iv) The manner and degree of co-operation with foreign firms considered necessary and desirable ;
- (v) Location of the industry and assistance required from Government in the development of industries, and the
- (vi) Stages in which industry should be developed.

The recommendations submitted by the Panels were considered by the Government of India in consultation with the Provincial authorities, and certain targets of production and expansion of capacity were accepted.

In the meantime, with the cessation of hostilities, the Department of Supply was amalgamated with the Department of Industries & Civil Supplies, and the new Department of Industry & Supply was created. The executive responsibility for carrying out the accepted recommendations of the various Panels was transferred to this new Department of Industry & Supply.

It will now be worthwhile to make a brief survey of the various developments that have taken place in the field of industry and also to indicate those that remain to be done.

The chemical industry occupies a key position in the economy of every country. Its products are used in a number of other industries such as Textiles, Paper, Leather, Soap, Glass, Ceramics, Paints, Plastics, Rayon, etc. The chemical industry, in India, in its modern form, really began after World War I (1914-18), although the oldest chemical factories were established in the middle of the last century. It was during World War I that real development took place. In 1921, there were 14 large chemical works employing 2500 workers. By 1939, the number of works rose to 38 employing about 8000 people. At present there are 200 firms employing 25,000 men.

Sulphuric acid.—There are now 40 firms, which can produce about 150,000 tons of sulphuric acid in 43 units. Of these, 11 are contact process units, mostly installed in the postwar period. The following table shows the consumption of sulphuric acid industry-wise:—

Chemicals	40%
Fertilisers	40
Metals	5
Cotton textile	5
Mineral oil	2
Leather	1
Engineering & other industries	7

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Four units are under erection, which would give an additional capacity of another 30,000 tons.

Superphosphate.—The production of superphosphate was negligible before

the war. At present, capacity exists for the production of 90,000 tons of superphosphate per annum and with the expansion schemes now in hand, it is expected that by the end of 1950, the production would reach the target figure of 100,000 tons per annum. The Government now purchases all superphosphate at a fixed price. This has helped considerably in increasing indigenous production.

Ammonium sulphate.—The Government of India decided that ammonium sulphate should be produced by the State on a large scale. A Commission was appointed in 1945 to report on the possibility of manufacture of ammonium sulphate in India. As a result of the recommendations made by this Commission, it was decided to start the production of ammonium sulphate at Sindhri with a capacity of 350,000 tons per annum. This factory is nearing completion and will be one of the biggest units in the world. There are two other units producing synthetic ammonia, one at Mysore and the other at Travancore, with an aggregate capacity of 56,000 tons per annum. The production of sulphate from the ammoniacal liquors of the coke ovens is 22,000 tons.

Bichromates.—India's production capacity now is 3000 tons per annum and the domestic consumption is only 1000 tons. We have a large exportable surplus and considerable quantities have been exported abroad.

Soda ash.—India's requirements of soda ash are about 120,000 tons per annum for her various industries.

Glass industry	30,000 tons
Silicates	15,000
Textiles	9,000
Paper	5,000
Chemical industry	6,000
Misc. requirements	10,000
Washing	45,000

Total 120,000

The present installed capacity is 54,000 tons. The chief difficulty in bridging this gap between production and domestic consumption is that of obtaining industrial salt at a reasonable price. The ideal location for the soda ash industry is naturally the coalfields which are situated a long way off from the Western coast, where cheap sea salt is available or from the salt-beds of Rajputana. The cost of transport is the principal limiting factor in the development of the soda ash industry.

Caustic soda.—India's requirements of caustic soda are 70,000 tons per annum, of which the soap industry consumes 31,500 tons, the textile industry, 19,250 tons, the paper industry 10,500 tons and other miscellaneous industries, 8,700 tons. The present installed capacity is 13,500 tons. There are certain units which are producing their own requirements of caustic soda and this capacity would come to another 3000 tons. At present, 3 units are under erection, which will give an additional capacity of 10,000 tons.

Liquid chlorine.—India has an installed capacity of 6,400 tons for the production of liquid chlorine. This is more than sufficient to meet all internal demands, but the difficulty is transport. Long distances involved stand in the way of free transport of liquid chlorine from the factories to places of consumption. Recently, a firm has planned the production of high test hypochlorite.

Bleaching powder.—India produces 5,160 tons of bleaching powder and plans for expanding the capacity are in hand.

Bromides.—From the bitters in the manufacture of salt, India has now established a capacity for the manufacture of 200 tons of bromides. The internal consumption has been computed to be 60 tons. There is ample scope for catering to the export market.

Magnesium chloride.—Another by-product in the manufacture of salt is magnesium chloride. India is not only able to meet her internal demands but has been exporting magnesium chloride to various countries including U.K.

Magnesium sulphate, alum, etc.—The demands for these chemicals are being fully met. There is also some export trade in these chemicals.

Potassium chlorate.—The match industry in India has expanded phenomenally during the last few years. At present, the country's aggregate capacity for the production of matches is 40 million gross boxes. We are also having a flourishing export trade in matches. To cater to the needs of the match industry we require a production of 2,000 tons of potassium chlorate. We are now mostly able to meet all internal demands for potassium chlorate.

Fine chemicals and pharmaceuticals.—The war found India totally unprepared to meet the growing needs of the Army. The procurement of medical stores for Government hospitals and the Army was the responsibility of the Director-General (I. M. S.), who was the head of the Medical Stores Department. The Medical Stores Department functioned primarily to supply the Army with all its medical and veterinary stores such as drugs, dressings, surgical instruments, etc. In addition to supplying the needs of the Army, the Medical Stores Department also provided for the needs of most of the Provincial Government and semi-Government hospitals, certain railways, mission hospitals, municipal institutions and other local bodies. The Medical Store Depots in India were the biggest importers of drugs and other medical stores and they were also manufacturers of drugs and dressings. There were five medical store depots maintained in five large centres in India. Two medical store depots had factories attached to them where certain preparations were made. These factories were at first located at Lahore and Calcutta but later on they were shifted to Madras and Bombay. At the outbreak of World War II, it was quickly realised that owing to shipping restrictions, these medical store depots would have to play a very large part in supplying to the growing needs of the Army, both at home and abroad. The organisation of the Director-General (I. M. S.) was strengthened by the recruitment of two officers, who were placed in charge of the production of Drugs and Dressings and Surgical Instruments and Appliances respectively. The result of intensive effort to increase production of medical stores was that the value of medical stores purchased in India (exclusive of depot manufactured articles) rose from Rs. 15.8 lakhs in 1938-39 to Rs. 3.48 crores in 1942-43.

Drugs and accessories needed for the Army could be roughly classified under the following headings.

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| (i) Galenicals | (vii) Special type of glassware. |
| (ii) Drugs of natural origin | (viii) Rubber goods |
| (iii) Vitamins and hormones | (ix) Surgical dressings |
| (iv) Synthetic drugs | (x) Ligatures |
| (v) Purified basic chemicals | (xi) Vaccines and sera |
| (vi) Laboratory stains and chemicals | (xii) Anti-biotics. |

India's requirements of galenicals were entirely met from indigenous sources. Surgical dressings, vaccines and sera, rubber goods, laboratory stains and chemicals were produced on a large scale. Of the drugs of natural origin, Morphine, Codeine, Strychnine, Caffeine, Ephedrine, Santonin, Quinine were produced in sufficient quantities not only for meeting internal demands, but, in some cases, for purposes of export. India's position regarding synthetic drugs was unsatisfactory, because the basic intermediates were in most cases unavailable. It was, however, possible to produce synthetically a very large number of drugs. A number of antiseptics and disinfectants, purgatives, uric acid solvents, vaso-constrictors, vaso-dilators, antipyretics, analgesics, narcotics, general anaesthetics and local anaesthetics were successfully produced. It can be said that given the equipment and the intermediate chemicals, there is not a single synthetic drug which is beyond the ability of an Indian chemist to produce.

During the war, an attempt was made to obtain intermediate chemicals. India is now able to produce 2 million gallons of benzene and 1 million gallons of toluene per annum at a cost which compares favourably with that prevailing in other countries. Recently, the manufacture of nitrobenzene at the Ordnance Factories has been established and it is now possible for the Indian industry to obtain about 100 tons of nitrobenzene at a price of Rs. 94/- per cwt. India produced very large quantities of T. N. T. during the war and, in fact, was one of the best sources of supply of this high explosive. It has not been difficult to establish the production of mono-nitrotoluenes which are now obtainable at a reasonable price. Manufacture was established for the production of 1000 tons of acetone from alcohol which is also now available for industrial purposes. During the war, it was felt necessary that the production of power alcohol should be taken in hand. At present, we have a capacity for the production of 14 million gallons of power alcohol in this country. Considerable quantities of butyl and amyl alcohol are also obtainable as by-products in this industry. The Indian coal is generally carbonised at a fairly high temperature with the result that the percentage of naphthalene hydrocarbons is rather high in the distillate. The production of naphthalene has been developed and we have now a capacity of 2000 tons of naphthalene per annum, which is capable of further expansion at a short notice. A certain amount of phthalic acid is also produced. The production of other basic chemicals such as Aniline, Hydroquinol, etc., has also been developed.

The development of the intermediate chemicals industry is closely bound up with the development of finished products. If this vicious circle is to be broken, then it occurs to me that it is necessary that a start should be made at the finished product end. I would not completely rule out a start being made by small units producing intermediate chemicals to feed the concerns producing finished products. It has been

said that the day of small business is over. This is not entirely correct. In the U. S. A., it has been found that a mass production concern is not equipped to handle small order and special jobs. These can be adequately handled by a small outfit which also supplies the needs of the big manufacturers. Even in the field of automobile industry, it has been noticed that a big manufacturer buys nearly 1,100 different items from 400 small firms. In the most specialised industry, namely, the Petroleum Industry, the five largest refining companies in the U. S. A. account for only 40% of the capacity. There are 170 small concerns who have been able to hold their own against the competition of the bigger manufacturers. Similarly 7 big chemical manufacturers depend on 120 small-size firms for many of their requirements. Bigger size does not necessarily mean the greater efficiency.

This was amply borne out during the war, when a small firm produced *para*-aminoacetanilide and supplied successfully all the big manufacturers of organo-arsenicals and organo-antimonials based on *para*-aminoacetanilide. The manufacture of certain types of fine chemical intermediates can easily be undertaken by our chemistry graduates with adequate research experience even on a very small scale. During the war, large quantities of imported commercial dyes were purified and converted into bacteriological stains. In fact, the entire demands for these laboratory stains were met from the supplies made by very small manufacturers.

Following is a list of important drugs which cover the whole field of chemotherapy. Items produced in India are marked with an asterisk.

Antiseptics and Disinfectants

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| *1. Phenol | †15. Methyl violet |
| 2. Salol | †16. Crystal violet |
| 3. Resorcinol | 17. Auramine |
| 4. Guaiacol, Guaiacol carbonate,
Guaiacol potassium sulphate | 18. Rivanol |
| *5. Thymol | 19. Rhodamine |
| 6. β -Naphthol | 20. Chinisol |
| *7. Tribromophenol | †21. Brilliant Green |
| 8. Iodoform | †22. Malachite Green |
| *9. Formaldehyde | 23. Trypan Red |
| *10. Hexamine | 24. Trypan Blue |
| *11. Chloramine T | 25. Mercurochrome |
| 12. Acriflavine | *26. Cresol |
| 13. Dermatol | *27. Chlorinated xylenols |
| *14. Protargol | *28. D. D. T. |

Purgatives and Aperitives

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| 1. Phenolphthalein | 2. Orexin (Phenyldihydroquinazoline) |
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Diuretics and uric acid solvents

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|---------------|-----------------|
| *1. Caffeine | 4. Salyrgan |
| 2. Piperazine | 6. Theophylline |
| *3. Atophan | 6. Theobromine |

* Are produced in India; in many cases, in insufficient quantities

† From imported intermediates.

Vaso-constrictors

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|----------------|-----------------------------------|
| *1. Adrenaline | 4. Alkaloids of Ergot: Ergotoxin, |
| *2. Ephedrine | Ergotamine, Ergometrin, |
| 3. Benzidine | Ergotinine, Tyramine. |

Vaso-dilators

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|------------------|--------------------|
| *1. Amyl nitrite | *3. Nitroglycerine |
| 2. Ethyl nitrite | 4. Octyl nitrite |

Antipyretics and analgesics

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|-------------------|---------------|
| *1. Acetanilide | 5. Aspirin |
| *2. Phenacetin | 6. Antipyrine |
| 3. Benzoic acid | 7. Pyramidone |
| 4. Salicylic acid | |

Narcotics and General Anaesthetics

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|---------------------|----------------|
| 1. Cyclopropane | *9. Chloroform |
| *2. Ether | 10. Avertine |
| *3. Para-aldehyde | 11. Veronal |
| 4. Acetophenone | *12. Luminal |
| *5. Chloroform | 13. Sulphonal |
| 6. Urethane | 14. Trional |
| 7. Adaline | 15. Tetronal |
| *8. Chloral hydrate | |

Local Anaesthetics

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|--------------------|---------------------|
| *1. Ethyl chloride | *4. Cocaine |
| 2. Anaesthesine | 5. Eucaine |
| 3. Novocaine | 6. Pentothal sodium |

Antiprotozoal and Antibacterial Drugs

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|-----------------------|-------------------|
| *1. Atoxyl | 10. Neostibosan |
| *2. Tryparsamide | 11. Neocardyl |
| *3. Carbarson | 12. Mercurochrome |
| *4. Neo-salvarsan | 13. Merthiolate |
| 5. Stovarsal | *14. Emetine |
| *6. Sulpharspneuamine | 15. Yatren |
| 7. Solusalvarsan | 16. Vioform |
| 8. Mapharside | 17. Sulpha drugs |
| *9. Urea Stibamine | (detailed below). |

Anti-malarials

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|------------------|----------------|
| 1. Quinine | 4. Mepacrine |
| 2. Aristochinine | 5. Paludrine |
| 3. Pamaquin | 6. Chloroquin. |

* Are produced in India ; in many cases, in insufficient quantities.

Sulphanilamide group of Drugs (Sulpha drugs)

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|--------------------|--|
| *1. Sulphanilamide | 8. Albucid |
| 2. Prontosil | 9. Dagenan |
| 3. Prontosil sol | 10. Sulphaguanidine |
| 4. Proseptazine | 11. Sulphathiazole |
| 5. Soluseptazine | 12. Sulphapyridine |
| 6. Rhodilone | 13. Sulphadiazine, sulphamerazine |
| *7. Ulerou | 14. <i>pp'</i> -Diaminodiphenylsulphone. |

Anti-biotics

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|-----------------|------------------|
| 1. Penicillin | 3. Chloromycetin |
| 2. Streptomycin | 4. Aureomycin |

Miscellaneous Drugs

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| *1. Camphor | 8. Sulphoform |
| *2. Ethyl ester of nicotinic acid
(coramines) | 9. Solganol |
| *3. Glycerophosphates and choline | 10. Mandelic acid |
| 4. Cardiazole | 11. S. V. P. 36 |
| 5. Cantharidine | *12. Iodohydroxyquinoline |
| *6. Calcium gluconate | *13. Kurchi bismuth iodide |
| 7. Anlinogen | *14. Emetine { from natural
*15. Santonine { sources. |

* Are produced in India: in many cases, in insufficient quantities.

It will be seen that there is a considerable scope for developing many items of manufacture which are at present not produced in India.

Development Plans in hand

We have been considering the question of production of Penicillin and other anti-biotics for a long time. In 1945, the Director-General of Supply financed an investigation for the production of Penicillin on a laboratory scale. Workers at the Institute of Science, Bangalore, and the Haffkine Institute, Bombay, have also been experimenting on the production of Penicillin. In March 1945, advantage was taken of the presence in England of Professor B. C. Guha, then an officer of the Department of Food, and a survey was undertaken by him on behalf of the Department of Supply of manufacture both in the U. K. and the U.S.A. The Department of Planning and Development sent out a team consisting of General Sir Saheb S. Sokhey and Dr. K. Ganapathy to investigate the possibility of manufacturing Penicillin in India. They submitted their report and certain investigations were made on the lines suggested in the Report. It was, however, felt that further investigations were necessary before a decision could be taken. Consequently, the Government of India sent out a second team consisting of General Sokhey, Dr. Ganapathy and Dr. Sankaran for the purpose. It has now been decided that the manufacture of Penicillin would be undertaken as a State enterprise in collaboration with a foreign firm. It is proposed to produce 1200 billion units per annum with a provision to increase it to 3600 billion units, if necessary. In the same factory, it is also proposed to manufacture certain sulpha drugs and synthetic antimalarials.

The collaboration of a foreign firm has been obtained for the production of *para*-aminosalicylic acid, a new curative agent in the treatment of tuberculosis. Certain proposals have been received for the manufacture of Polystyrene required as a raw material for the plastic industry. A scheme for the production of Phenol on a large scale has been worked out and is under examination. A foreign firm is interested in manufacturing this in collaboration with an Indian firm. Three firms have been granted licences for the large-scale production of acetic acid and acetic anhydride. The aggregate production would come to about 3,000 tons per annum, which will be more than sufficient for India's present internal requirements. A large plant for the production of acetate rayon is also under erection. This plant will be producing its own acetic anhydride.

A British firm has already undertaken an extensive survey about the possibility of manufacturing certain industrial explosives. The scheme will be considered by the Government of India as soon as possible.

India consumes about 180 million gallons of motor spirit, 66,000 tons of kerosene, about 30,000 tons of various diesel oils and 53,000 tons of furnace oil every year. The Indian production of motor spirit (natural) is only 15 million gallons, that of kerosene 4000 tons and about 4000 tons of various diesel oils. This is an extremely unsatisfactory position. The Government decided in May 1948 to get from Messrs. Koppers Inc., Pittsburgh a report on the possibility of manufacture of synthetic oil from coal. Messrs. Koppers undertook an elaborate investigation and submitted their report which is now under the consideration of the Government of India. Several other offers have also been received from foreign firms.

An extensive survey was also undertaken about the occurrence of suitable low grade coal required for the purpose. It has been found that extensive deposits are available which can be worked by the strip mining method to give all the coal required for such a project at an economical rate. The low temperature carbonisation of this coal will produce a char suitable as domestic fuel and the tar could be processed to aviation petrol. A part of the char can be used for gasification to produce synthesis gas and also hydrogen needed for the hydrogenation of tar. If such a scheme is adopted, a considerable amount of oxygenated hydrocarbons will be obtained as a by-product which will be admirably suited as a starting material for the preparation of various organic substances used in commerce.

Under the auspices of the Damodar Valley Authority the Governments of Bihar and West Bengal in collaboration with the Government of India brought out some specialists from Germany to report on the possibility of establishing the dyestuff industry in the Damodar Valley area. Other independent investigations were also carried out by some firms. The whole matter is under consideration. Of the various dyes that are largely used in this country, there are a few items which account for a large proportion of our imports of dyestuffs. These are :

- (i) Alizarine group of dyes including vat dyes of the anthracene group.
- (ii) Congo red
- (iii) Rapid fast colours
- (iv) Vat dyes such as Indigo, Carbazol blue, etc.

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|---------------------|------------------------|
| (v) Sulphur black | (vii) Rhodamines |
| (vi) Metanil yellow | (viii) Chrome colours. |

A full investigation has been made of the various quantities of intermediate chemicals that will be needed for the manufacture of these dyes. The analysis shows that it is possible to produce some of these dyestuffs economically in this country, as most of the intermediates will be available from existing or future production of chemicals which has been planned.

Plans are also in hand for the production of Methanol and formaldehyde at Sindhri.

In view of the very large development that has taken place in the production of plastic articles in this country, it is necessary that the manufacture of moulding powders should be taken in hand early. At present only one firm is producing Phenol-formaldehyde resin but not in sufficient quantity. There are now about 40 firms producing plastic articles in India with an aggregate consumption capacity of 3,000 tons of Phenol-formaldehyde resin, 2500 tons of Polystyrene and large quantities of other moulding powders. In view of the importance of phenol as an intermediate for the various industries, such as Dyestuffs, Pharmaceuticals and Plastics, an American firm is considering putting up a plant for the production of phenol.

Plywood.—There has been very large development of the production of plywood needed both for the fabrication of tea chests and also for commercial purposes. There are at presents 45 firms producing nearly 80 million sq. feet of plywood for tea chests and about 20 million sq. feet for commercial plywood. The establishment of plastic resins would go a long way to meet the demands for the plywood industry's requirements of various types of resins. Plans have also been formulated for the production of Urea at Sindhri; when the plan materialises, the production of Urea-formaldehyde resin will not be difficult.

Raw films.—India is the world's second largest producer of cinema films. It is therefore extremely important that India develops the production of raw films. Co-operation of a Swiss group has been sought for the production of raw films in India.

Mention has already been made about the project for the manufacture of ammonium sulphate at Sindhri. The connected load of the fertilizer factory is, as at present planned, about 45,000 K. W., added to which there is a big demand for steam for process work. In view of the necessity for supplying additional power from Sindhri to the Bihar grid, it was decided to generate 80,000 K. W. at Sindhri with room for expansion to 200,000 K. W. if need be. The various River Valley schemes which are under planning will also need very large quantities of high tension insulators, which are at present not produced in the country. A survey has been undertaken as to the possibility of producing High Tension Insulators in India. The scheme is now under examination.

Steel.—The planning for the production of steel is the responsibility of the Engineering Section of the Directorate General of Industries & Supplies, but a brief mention may be made about the position of steel in this country, as the development of chemical group of industries is intimately connected with the question of production of steel. In January 1945, the Department of Planning & Development having provisionally

assessed the immediate postwar steel requirements of India at 3 million tons as against the then production capacity of 1.2 million tons, appointed a committee to investigate the possibility of attaining the target which was provisionally fixed by the Government at 3 million tons. Three firms of international reputation were entrusted with the task of reporting on the possibility of India's attaining this target.

India, one of the very few nations of the world endowed by Nature with an abundant supply of high quality raw materials required for the manufacture of steel and with 20% of the world's population, now has less than 1% of the world's steel production. The present steel expansion plan represents only the initial and immediate step in the ultimate programme to place our country among the major steel producing areas of the world. The three firms entrusted with the task have now submitted their reports which are under examination by the Government of India.

Cement.—Closely associated with the requirement of steel is that of cement. India today has got an installed capacity for the production of 2.7 million tons of cement in 21 units. Three new factories are under erection and seven factories are expanding their capacity. It is expected that by the middle of 1950 we will have attained a target of 3.5 million tons. India's present internal consumption is about 4 million tons and with the development of various River Valley Projects, the consumption is expected to go up by another 2 million tons within the next few years.

Paper.—India's present production of paper is only 110,000 tons per annum. With the growth of literacy, it is estimated that the consumption of paper will increase considerably. The immediate target to be achieved by 1951 has been fixed at 200,000 tons. Fifteen firms are already producing paper at the rate of 110,000 tons per annum. Six of these firms have decided to expand their capacities by another 50,000 tons. Four new units are coming into production by the end of 1950, with an additional capacity of 43,000 tons. It will, therefore, be seen that the target fixed will be reached in time.

Leather.—The export of tanned hides and leather products gives India valuable foreign exchange. India's total foreign exchange earned in this group of products has been in the neighbourhood of Rs. 19 crores per annum. It is, therefore, important to make this industry as self-sufficient as possible with respect to its requirements of chemicals and tanning substances. It has already been mentioned that India is now fully capable of meeting all demands for chromium compounds. The question of producing certain types of Synthas and finishing chemicals is also engaging attention.

Rayon.—It has already been mentioned that one unit for producing acetate rayon is under erection. Two other units will soon be going into production of rayon by the viscose process. Arrangements have been made for the production of carbon bisulphide, caustic soda and other chemicals required for keeping these plants in production. A reed has been found which after processing gives good pulp suitable for use in rayon manufacture. This reed has been found to have as high as 95% of α -cellulose. Pilot plant trials have been made with regard to the suitability of this reed and if the large-scale trials which are under test succeed, then one of the most important problems facing the rayon industry would be solved.

Rubber.—India produces about 18,000 tons of natural rubber per annum. Its consumption in the rubber processing factories has been estimated to be about

20,000 to 22,000 tons. It will therefore seem that we are more or less self-sufficient with regard to our requirements of natural rubber. India now produces all her requirements of tyres and tubes and has also a fairly large exportable surplus. At present, accelerators, vulcanisers and other rubber chemicals are imported. Large quantities of carbon black are required to be imported for this industry. The production of these rubber chemicals is an important necessity which should receive immediate attention. We are importing every year nearly Rs. 3 crores worth of various rubber chemicals and dyes.

It will be seen that the developments mentioned and also others which are in hand will need a considerable amount of capital investment. The Government of India have now declared, in unequivocal terms, the conditions under which they would welcome the participation of foreign firms in the industrial development of India. It is gratifying to note that during the last fifteen months a considerable amount of foreign capital has been invested in India.

Apart from the question of capital formation, the most important requirement of industry is its valuable raw material, namely, technical personnel. The Government of India undertook an investigation of the Scientific Man-power position of the country. Since 1945, a scheme of sending science graduates for training abroad has also been inaugurated. A large number of students have been sent abroad for higher technical training. Owing to the postwar rush of students in the various foreign universities, it has often been found extremely difficult to secure adequate theoretical and practical training for these scholars. It is therefore imperative that the facilities available for technical training in India should be utilised to the fullest extent before a scholar is sent abroad, for further studies. It was suggested that a priority list of subjects should be drawn up and the subjects in which training in India cannot be imparted adequately should be given preference over other subjects. It is recognised that the Universities have been sadly depleted of their teaching personnel on account of the very poor scales of pay that prevail there. As far as I know, there has been hardly any revision of the scales of pay which were fixed after World War I. The cost of living index has gone up by over 300%. Today it is impossible for a university teacher to keep the wolf from the door with the pay which he is offered. He has therefore no option but to seek other avenues of employment. The effect of this diversion of really capable men from the teaching profession will be felt within a few years when perhaps it would be too late to remedy the situation. It is true that a large number of National Laboratories with attractive scales of pay are being established in various subjects but these Laboratories can hardly be expected to fulfil the functions of a University. In England, the National Chemical Laboratory is charged with the responsibility of carrying out research in the national interest for the benefit of the community and to meet the requirements of Government Departments.

According to the Director of Chemical Research Laboratory, Teddington, there are four kinds of work which are suited to the Laboratory's programme :

- (1) Research leading to fundamental reference data of general value.

The universities would hardly be interested in undertaking this sort of an investigation which would require laborious work for a number of years.

(2) New methods and techniques of chemistry in which it is desirable that an expert group should be maintained.

In this group would fall the development of, say, high pressure technique, micro-analysis, radiometry, etc.

(3) Work dealing with the utilization of indigenous raw materials and with the concentration of low grade substances.

(4) The conservation of essential raw materials.

It appears, therefore, that in England, the National Laboratories fulfil definite functions. If a similar plan is adopted for the National Laboratories in India, it will be clear that so far as the general training of a student or initiating him into the methods of research is concerned, the Universities will still have to play their role unaided. It will, therefore, be a great disaster if the Universities get depleted of their talents because of the low scales of pay given to the teachers. There are also a certain number of research establishments specialising in sugar, lac, cotton, etc. maintained by various Government Departments. A considerable difference in the scale of pay of research staff exists in these institutions. The inevitable result of such a disparity is that the best talent tends to gravitate towards that research centre which provides the best terms and conditions of service. This is often not to the best interest either of the worker or of the nation.

It has been stated that the Universities do not have adequate funds at their disposal to better the lot of teachers. But, of late, a tendency to multiply the post-graduate teaching and research departments in the same university has been noticeable. As most of the universities have not adequate funds at their disposal to run the existing departments properly and to bring them to a higher level, such a tendency will have the effect of lowering the general standard of teaching and research. It is not at all necessary for each university to have all conceivable departments of teaching and research. One university can *give more emphasis* to a few subjects and bring them to a higher level leaving other universities to do the same in respect of remaining subjects. It is also necessary that an uniform scale of pay should prevail in the different universities and there should be possibility of interchange of teachers and professors for definite periods.

Apart from the question of pay of University teachers, another handicap of the University worker is the very small research grant he gets to pursue his subject. Even with the best of intentions, it is not possible to do much unless funds are available for procuring equipment and chemicals needed for an investigation. The Board of Scientific & Industrial Research gives grants to some University workers for investigations of specific subjects. Research made to order is not the same thing as research which a worker wishes to pursue on his own accord.

Attempts have also been made to import foreign technicians to meet the requirements of industry for specialists. 37 German technicians have been brought

out to India with the help of Directorate General of Industries & Supplies for various industries. Eighteen more technicians will shortly be arriving in India. Besides these, certain British, American and Japanese technicians have also come out to India. As a condition precedent to allowing a foreign firm to operate in this country, it has been stipulated that the Indian personnel should be trained to take up full charge of the industry within a definite period. All these are palliative measures. But it is to be recognised that the technicians will have to be trained within the country. We cannot depend for ever on technical help from outside. It is, therefore, all the more important that the present anaemic state of the finances of universities should be remedied. The universities ought to be in a position to keep the best men available for training technical graduates in the method of research. The importance of research cannot be over-emphasised even from the point of view of industrial development. A person, who has spent a number of years in fundamental research is definitely better suited to take up an industrial career than a person who has specialised early in Industrial Chemistry. The good name of India will depend on the quality of research workers turned out by the universities and her industrial future will largely be determined by her ability to produce investigators of merit. It will not do to have confused ideas regarding the relative importance of fundamental knowledge and its practical application. Attempts to train personnel in the practical application of science against a background of an imperfect education in pure science can only give rise to people, who as my predecessor remarked, "will at the most be able to mend what we have but not build what we want."

Another serious handicap in our existing set up is the low status which a technical man generally occupies in Industry. Unless we safeguard security of tenure and adequate status of the technical man in Industry, we run grave risks.

The question of training research workers also raises the important question of medium of instruction. My predecessor, in his address at Allahabad, fully dwelt on this question at some length. It goes without saying that training and instructions, in order to be easily grasped, should be imparted in the mother tongue of the pupils. On the other hand, Science is international in character and has developed through the co-operative efforts of all lands. This co-operation occurs in the form of mental contacts and exchange of ideas. I fully agree with the conclusions, which my predecessor came to on this question. We shall have to depend on English in order to consult scientific literature and journals; we shall have to publish results of our investigations in English. Our present system of scientific education has been in vogue for nearly a century. Any radical change or transformation in it cannot be effected without arresting its progress for a while. Such a break will be disastrous when we are struggling to take our rightful place in the comunity of free nations.

With the partition of the country, the Food situation in India has become extremely acute. We have now to make large imports of foodgrains, which consume a very considerable portion of our foreign exchange resources. At present, in India, about 75% of the population is engaged in agricultural pursuits. We will now have to divert at least 25% of the population to the Industry, so that we can earn enough foreign exchange to pay for our large imports of capital goods. Uptil now we have

been largely depending on the exports of our minerals in order to earn necessary foreign exchange. India has supplied 40 million tons of high grade manganese ores since 1910 to the world at a price but little above the cost of mining and transport. Similarly, large exports of mica, chromite, magnesite, sillimanite and kyanite had to be maintained to procure foreign exchange. These resources are expendable resources and once we are depleted of these minerals, there will be no means of replacing these. The critical shortage in metals has been most seriously felt up to now only in respect of tin, zinc and lead. But signs are appearing that accessible deposits of copper, nickel, antimony in the world are diminishing. A policy of conservation will, therefore, have to be followed with respect to some of these minerals. If that is done, India will have to depend on her exports of industrial products for earning her foreign exchange. This can only be done by developing industries on a well-planned and co-ordinated basis. Scientific man-power, industrial raw materials and other natural resources will have to be rigidly planned. In this task, the Indian Chemical Society will naturally play an important role. It is imperative that our Society remains completely aloof from political influences and the members take a detached view of the national problems and are able to offer their advice in a most free and frank manner.